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‘Comparisons are odious’: or are there lessons to be learnt?

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ABSTRACT

Engineering is taught in many ways and at different levels, hence are we being optimistic to try to learn from each other. Although there are significant changes occurring in engineering education, it is essential not to overlook some of the key aspects, which must underpin any education curriculum. Key common issues and challenges that are associated with two very diverse institutions, are discussed. While this is not a formal ‘cross-sparring’ exercise these issues highlight important common concerns, which include attractiveness, meeting changing student demands and expectations, responding to changing employer needs and to central government pressures in education and research.

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INTRODUCTION

Countless universities across Europe teach engineering, with a wide range of topics taught in diverse ways and at different levels. What can we hope to learn from comparisons, which cover all engineering disciplines and orientations; or, are there indeed common criteria that we can use for comparison? Recent publications [1], [2] would suggest that currently there are significant changes associated with engineering education. While this may well be correct, but in addressing such issues we would be wise not to overlook some of the key aspects which must underpin any education curriculum. To do this we draw on direct experience from two very different institutions, having different missions and located in two different countries. While there may be

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great differences in many things, there are also important features and challenges that not only are common to both, but should be also of general concern to all engineering educators. Although within the context of this paper we will not be undertaking a 'cross-sparring' exercise [3], as these are major benchmarking type of exercises in their own right, we are also aware of the power of such approaches.

1 INTRODUCTION TO THE INSTITUTIONS

We first give a brief portrait of the two institutions, both of which have very clear strategies [4], [5] that are reviewed regularly. Although both are higher education institutions, superficially it might seem that these two could have little in common. However that is very misleading.

1.1 Metropolia University of Applied Sciences

Metropolia is the largest University of Applied Sciences in Finland. It educates about half of all the Bachelor of Engineering graduates of the country and in addition offers Master of Engineering programmes. In the Finnish university system higher education in technology is additionally offered in science universities leading to Bachelor or Master of Science degrees. Last year there were 15 300 Bachelor students (with 3850 graduating of which 7% were international) and 1320 post graduate students (with 570 graduating with masters degrees of which 13% were international.). The total staff count was slightly less than 1000. Until the end of last year all the degree programmes had been free from fees for everyone. This is expected to change at the start of the next academic year for non EU/ETA area students.

The main goals of Metropolia are in the area of education, research, development and innovation (RDI) activities as well as societal impact and regional development activities. The engineering graduates are mainly employed by the industries in the greater Helsinki area. The instruction language is mainly Finnish however, there are 8 engineering programmes where instruction is in English. The focus of the University is on high-quality learning and professional life cooperation. The operating culture and expertise are renewed through digitalisation and campus development. In terms of RDI and business solutions, Metropolia is seeking growth especially in impact and external funding.

1.2 Imperial College London

Imperial College London is a science-based university located in the heart of London, committed to developing the next generation of researchers, scientists and academics through collaboration across disciplines. It is a multidisciplinary space for education, research, innovation, translation and commercialisation, aiming at to tackle global challenges. It has an international reputation for excellence in teaching and research and is consistently rated amongst the world's best universities. Excellence in education is at the core of Imperial's ethos and is reflected in both UK and international rankings. It also contains the greatest concentration of high-impact research of any major UK university. At various times Imperial has been home for 14 Nobel laureates and two Fields Medallists.

The origins of the institution can be traced back to the middle of the nineteenth century with the separate founding of the Royal Colleges of Chemistry and of Science, the Royal School of Mines and the City and Guilds College for engineering. These merged to form Imperial College. The nineteenth century also saw the creation of several different medical schools within London. In 1988 St Mary's Hospital Medical School

became the first of these to merge with Imperial. Then in 1997 several other schools joined to make what is now the largest medical school in Europe.

Today Imperial is home to 15,700 students and 8,000 staff (2015/2016 statistics). Undergraduates are attracted from more than 125 countries. Fees are charged at one rate for UK and EU students and a higher rate for those coming from other parts of the world. The faculty of engineering includes 4060 undergraduates and 2763 postgraduates (2015/2016) with 381 academic staff and 830 research staff. The student:staff ratio is 16.9 and the applicants for student admission is between 7:1 to 8:1 for both undergraduates and postgraduates.

2 IDENTIFICATION OF COMMON THEMES

In their different ways both institutions face challenges associated with a range of issues. Both institutions get mainly young people to start university studies with great expectations of attractive and rewarding carrier afterwards. The challenge for the universities is to organise learning opportunities for the students to get the relevant competences and skills applicable not only at the start of a working life but additionally to enable them to continuously update of their market value. Furthermore both institutions receive some fraction of their financing according to the different indicators, which can broadly be captured within the following themes and quality metrics.

2.1 Attractiveness

What makes engineering education and the profession attractive might vary in different countries and different institutions. Branding both the institutions and the comparisons to describe their focused profile, would help the communication with different stakeholders. Furthermore the branding needs to be marketed though today's more varied channels - social media - to reach the relevant target groups.

In Imperial College London the attractiveness might lie in the challenging theoretical thinking, analysing technical problems, creating new theories and inventing solutions to unsolved problems. However in Metropolia the attractiveness might be based on the work profile by combining and adopting methods and theories to new solutions, running, controlling and developing processes, building and managing products and systems.

Important for the successful recruiting of students is the correct kind of information about the studies; expected theoretical level, intensity, expected learning outcomes, the level of freedom in schedules, methods and content. Furthermore the need of creativity, business mind and entrepreneurship are forming the brand of the university.

The brand of a university also attracts potential companies to seek cooperation with the institution and recruit its graduates. However at the same time the companies involved are influencing the brand of the university and the employability of its graduates in relevant positions plays an essential role in attractiveness.

When students are choosing engineering education, tuition fees have started to play an important role. While in Europe some decades ago, most of education was offered free or almost free - since then in many of the countries the situation has changed. In England the turning point came in 1998 when the Labour government introduced yearly tuition fees of £1,000. That has now increased to the level of £9,000. In Finland all degree tuition is still free for EU/ETA students, but this year the first time students from outside the EU/ETA area will need to pay. The debate about the effects of this is very

active. How fees are affecting attractiveness is another question - is expensive education more appreciated, will it attract better teachers, will the employers appreciate more the graduates from expensive programmes?

Comparisons between institutions and countries about the tuition fees and their influence could help future policy makers to develop payment strategies to a direction that best supports the universities to fulfil their mission.

2.2 Meeting changing student demands and expectations

The first impression of the studies is important as during the first semester they start to discover their own attitude and aptitude for studying and taking responsibility for their own learning. The University needs to be alert to guiding the students to establish their style, including result orientation and effectiveness. Once the students have started the studies they have already invested effort which should be proven profitable. However, growth towards being a professional engineer or scientist takes the whole of the time until graduation. Furthermore it becomes important for students to develop an appreciation that lifelong learning should continue through their career.

Today's students have lived their entire life in the digital environment having different manners of nature of communication than many of the staff members of the university. Searching for information, understanding the origin and reliability of it and expressing their own thought, ideas and deliverables have taken a totally new form. Importantly however this new format of information has not changed the fact that in engineering education the need for a sound understanding of mathematics and natural sciences continues to remain critical.

For students and potential students it would be helpful to get information about the comparisons of pedagogical methods and paradigms used in different universities, although this might be difficult to achieve. Furthermore, comparisons of the student experiences, future employability, working life cooperation and institution branding etc., would be appreciated when the place for studies is chosen.

2.3 Meeting changing employer needs

Employer needs are rapidly changing. Sadly enough, when employers are asked about the competence needs of their recruits, they tend to list skills which are needed immediately. Employers tend to not to notice the competences that create the base of understanding that underpins the continued development of knowledge. In other words, this can overlook or take for granted the fact that there is still the essential requirement for them to possess a sound grasp of their engineering fundamentals, otherwise the rest is just froth!

As mentioned in the World Economic Forum White Paper "On average, a third of the skillsets required to perform in today's jobs will be wholly new by 2020. [2] In that report there is introduced a framework for transforming education ecosystems with 8 collaborative action areas giving roles for both public and private sector. Although in many European countries educational policy, skill needs information is commonly used to inform curriculum development [6] there are still huge challenges in creating right skills. So while in one sense the WEF White Paper is correct it should also be remembered that this does not apply to the subject fundamentals.

2.4 Mismatch of expectations

Taking note of the previous comments one might come to wonder if there is a mismatch between how the young professionals of today, also known as the 'millennials' are attracted and how the employers want to attract them. Despite the importance of employees and how to motivate them and create an environment where they can thrive

and fulfil themselves by contributing to a higher purpose, one has to keep in mind that the fundamental reason of companies is to create economic value for its investors. Over the last decades, a trend of job tasks becoming more advanced and demanding a higher level of knowledge has been evident. As people become more educated, and more companies apply a project or process-oriented structure, people are able to see how their role contributes to the overall business and value creation for the customer. This also affects how people can be motivated; for example – it can be seen that the millennials view and value internal rewards more highly than previous generations, indicating that this will become even more important for companies to deal with when they want to attract and retain talents. A common trend is that millennials strive for a job where they can contribute to a higher purpose, have opportunities for personal development and fulfil themselves via their work. It is a matter of a hierarchy of social needs among employees and what it is that drives and attracts people. In short, corresponding to Maslow's 'self-actualisation level of motivation', according to which people are driven by a chance to satisfy their higher level needs like self-fulfilment, self-control and professional autonomy and thus, 'participative management' style is optimal way to manage people within organization.[7]

One example of the new working style in cooperation with different stakeholders is Sandvik's Open Innovation portal that invites individual inventors, small business and listed companies to propose innovative solutions to a number of specific challenges. The company also encourages its own employees to use the portal for releasing creativity and utilising their collective knowledge on customer's applications and products. Pasi Kangas (Vice President and Head of R&D at Sandvik Materials Technology): "We are optimistic that open innovation will lead to new products and technologies that aren't otherwise possible. Great ideas really can come from anyone, anywhere. We want to find them and give them every opportunity to make it real – to make a bigger difference – for all our sakes as we look to shape a more sustainable future." [8]

These views differ greatly from the traditional stereotypical view of engineering work that might focus on one restricted problem individually or in a small team. Instead, adopting knowledge, networking and sharing but still carrying strong responsibility of the outcomes is based on deep understanding of science and the "big picture" in the contemporary world.

3 QUALITY

Quality within a University is a multi-dimensional issue. The focus might lay in system, management, enhancement, improvement, measurement, comparison, benchmarking, cross-sparring or ranking etc. The target can be the whole university or some functions or features of it, such as education, research, societal impact, employer satisfaction, student satisfaction, financing etc. Furthermore the level of the inspection might be the whole university, one faculty or department, one study programme or research group, or even an individual course. However, the viewpoint varies additionally by the viewer - whether the activity is for internal use or for marketing purposes.

It is essential to have a clear view what is the background and purpose of comparing universities. The value of indicators is totally dependent on the correct feature of the definition and its measurement. Otherwise the indicators might be totally misleading and one can prove whatever with them and thereby learn nothing. A misleading

indicator can lead to partial optimisation and therefore instead of improvement cause disruption for the agreed bigger target.

In European countries financial incentives are widely used for steering decisions towards better quality in universities [9]. However, the discussion of quality can be entered at least from three different angles: rankings, quality labels and continuous development.

3.1 Ranking

There are many ranking lists of universities, with the best known international ones mainly focusing on research and publications [10]. Educational success is more demanding to measure and subjective, thus the rankings are not that popular. In UK the Teaching Excellence Framework [11] is introducing the list that aims to recognise and reward excellence in teaching and learning and help inform prospective students' choices for higher education. Such list does not exist in Finland neither in wider international extent.

Although only few people appear to know the indicators behind different ranking lists, they have much power over the reputation of the university. The reputation might attract students and staff additionally to facilitating partnerships from working life.

3.2. Quality labels

In Finland the Finnish Education Evaluation Centre (FINEEC) is responsible for the evaluation of education provided by universities and universities of applied sciences (UAS). The three key evaluation types are the audits of higher education institutions' (HEIs) quality systems, thematic evaluations of the education system and engineering degree programme reviews. The Polytechnics (UAS) Act and the Universities Act obligate HEIs to participate regularly in the external evaluation of their operations and quality systems. After passing the audit, the HEI will receive a quality label valid for six years. The reports of each audit are publicly available in the www pages of FINEEC (<https://karvi.fi/en/higher-education/>),

In UK the Higher Education Funding Council (HEFCE) conducts regular teaching audits of all higher education institutions on a rotational basis, with the principal conclusions. (The 'E' indicates England as each of the individual regions have their own, broadly similar Councils.) Such audits, while conducted under the auspices of the funding Council who involve appropriate senior academics from other institutions. A synopsis of the audit findings are available on a public basis. New legislation currently being discussed within the Parliament would link the outcomes of such audits to the level of central funding received by institutions – probably in three banding levels – and also to the student fee level that can be levelled. This is a mixed blessing while on the one hand this can be seen as an important step in raising the importance of education in ALL academic institutions, on the other hand this can be seen also as a further step in the removal of autonomy from institutions and a greater hand of central government exerting increased control over them.

Becoming a 'Chartered Engineer' is an important step to full engineering professional status in the UK. As part of the criteria for this an engineer should have followed a degree programme recognised by the appropriate professional body. Hence for example, to become a chartered civil engineer it is first necessary to have followed an undergraduate programme to Masters level approved by the Institution of Civil Engineers. For a Civil Engineering Department to offer such a programme it's course must also be approved by the Institution. In a similar manner to the HEFCE reviews there would be a paper evaluation and a visit by an approval team. The composition

of this team and the assessment criteria would be different from the HEFCE review in that there would be more emphasis on the suitability of the programme in laying the foundations of professional competence. As with the HEFCE reviews such reviews are repeated on a regular cycle, say every 5 years.

3.3. Continuous development

Continuous development is based on good knowledge of the present situation and clear vision of the desired condition.

Defining present situation starts by collecting existing facts and then executing a self-evaluation. The results of the self-evaluation can be analysed with the help of SWOT analysis or some other tools that assist on defining the most urgent and essential development areas.

According to a research done with ERASMUS+ financing [3] an effective method for identifying good practices and other ideas for the enhancement is to meet “critical friends” in a cross-sparring session focusing on the first priority development areas. These critical friends are typically from another university and having as their strength the areas which are the chosen development areas of the original university. The friends will introduce and share their good practises and give hints for enhancement. Vice versa the roles will be changed and thus such an activity helps both of the parties in a constructive way.

In continuous development it is important to make the decisions of the actions and also execute the follow up of the implementation. Update of documentation supports the share of right knowledge in the organisation.

In the open culture of development the documentation of the enhancement and current practices is available for the review of all the interested parties. Potential students, students, staff and other stakeholders then have an opportunity to compare and build their own understanding of the attractiveness of the institution.

4 SUMMARY

Engineering education in different countries and at different levels is in a key position to teach people to find solutions to the greatest challenges facing the world and hence advance the wellbeing of human life. The big issue for the profession and its educators is to make this fact better known and encourage talented students to find and choose the right type of studies. The engineering studies need to be strongly branded as the starting point for gaining the competences and skills for solving these problems. The key role in this branding is the trustable evidence of the strengths of each institution that are given visibility for comparisons by the quality documentation, accreditations and rankings. Additionally much knowledge about the job opportunities and achievements should be marketed.

Comparisons that bridge between diverse institutions can offer effective tools for improvements and help to attract appropriate students and other stakeholders to find right partners to cooperate in such activities. Comparisons between institutions and countries can be extremely beneficial, raising relevant information for different stakeholders, be they students, employers, financing bodies and to support the directions of internal development. However, as there is a huge variety of institutions and missions the comparisons need to be understood accordingly. Still in their different and diverse ways there are common themes that offer challenges and similar methodologies that can be adopted for their appraisal, development, branding and ways to increase their attractiveness.

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